

Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage

Research Report

An investigation into whether Vinnytsia's Architectural heritage is evidence of historic multiculturalism

Vinnytsia Architecture as Evidence of Multiculturalism

Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural heritage and verifying whether it constitutes as evidence of historic multiculturalism

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Abstract

The term multiculturalism in the last decade has become a new point of discussion used to debate the progression of a society in reaching a desired stage of neoliberal idea of progress made possible by its advancements in a globalised world. Therefore, the claim is the present of multiculturalism or a multicultural society is only possible to find in the last decade. However, if one looks critically back at history they will find eras with successful multicultural societies, many later becoming empires. It could be argued that one of the reasons these empires become so large was due to the present of a multicultural society. Therefore, this research is going to explore the topic of a historic multicultural society and construct a method of investigation needed for a framework that can verify the presents of historic multiculturalism in a historic society. Then apply this method to the case study of Vinnytsia, a city in central Ukraine, to check if the idea and present of historic multiculturalism is a valid concept.

Savoy Hotel in the Centre Of Vinnytsia, Page 315: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Introduction

Multiculturalism is a term used during the last decade as a marker of success in a Neo-liberal world view, pushing forward the ideas of Francis Fukuyama and his end of history theory that societies will reach a final evolutionary stage made possible by a globalised world.ⁱ However, the word multicultural, or multiculturalism, is much harder to define than one may assume in the fields of International Relations (IR), Political or Social Sciences. Yet to a historian the idea of a multicultural society may not be as new of a concept as one might think. A historian could even argue that the idea of a multicultural society was the norm and possibly a marker of success in historical societies. One example is the Roman Empire where they mixed with many other races so that it is hard to claim there was a pure race of Romans for Roman ethnicity at its core was mixed.ⁱⁱ In fact, it could be argued that this mixed ethnicity as a result of conquest may be one of the reasons why the Romans succeeded in controlling such a large empire and maintained political control over vast populations. If true, this would make the idea of a multicultural society more the norm than the exception within the wider histography of mankind.

An analytical framework to test whether multiculturalism can be found in a historic society has not yet been developed. Therefore, this research has to first develop a method of investigation to verify the idea of the existence of a historic multicultural society. This consists of a clear set of definitions of what constitutes a historic multicultural society and methods to test the hypotheses in a framework of analysis in a historic case study to validate whether the idea of a historic multicultural society is a valid theory to help better explain history. This research uses the architectural history of Vinnytsia,

one of the largest cities in central Ukraine, as a case study. The city of Vinnytsia has a long history with evidence of a settlement first being established around the bronze age. The city had favourable agricultural surroundings and its strategic location along the Boh River gave it a natural defence and helped it establish its position as a trading hub. This strategic location meant that throughout the city's history many outsiders came and settled in the region bringing with them many different cultures and customs giving probable cause of the existence of a multicultural society.

Testing for multiculturalism can be done using the city's architectural history because one finds three prominent eras; the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the Russian Empire, and the Soviet Union. The remains of architecture from all three eras can still be seen in contemporary Vinnytsia and can be used as a historical model to set the parameters of what could constitute a historic multicultural city/society to inform a wider debate about historic multiculturalism is. This research will use a newly constructed framework from the current academic literature on multiculturalism from the social sciences to build a new theoretical framework of analysis for historic case studies as a way of bringing these studies into the current academic debate. It supports the idea that multiculturalism was a primary factor of how a society or city became successful in today's world and in a wider histography.

Literature Review

Given the difficulty of defining a term like multiculturalism, due to its broad range in many different academic fields, careful steps must be taken when using the term historic multiculturalism. Therefore, this literature review will first explore search terms in google scholar and see the number of hits to narrow down our word choice. Then, it will group papers by field of study to chart the different authors' uses and definition of multiculturalism. Lastly, the literature review will explore other scholars' theoretical frameworks to build a theoretical framework of analysis for this study.

Search Terms

A Google Scholar search on "multiculturalism" returns 712,000 hits giving us a broad spectrum of articles and books. When we refine this search to "multiculturalism theoretical framework" we get 466,000 hits and articles mainly dealing with social science theories around integration, assimilation, racism, global political order and identity politics. Finally, a search on "historic multiculturalism" returns 169,000 hits and a search on "multiculturalism architecture" returns 60,400 hits. Many of the found articles deal with topics and policies on integration of minority groups into society, identity politics, race/racism, ethnicity and education.

The word multiculturalism is heavily used in Public Policy aimed at improving racism, integration, and assimilation in both immigration and education. Examples are articles: "Multiculturalism" by Tariq Mododⁱⁱⁱ, and "Rethinking Multiculturalism After its "Retreat": Lessons From Canada" By Elke Winter^{iv}. Modod argues that the term multiculturalism is difficult to define given that both the critics and defenders often mix the term when debating integration and assimilation policies. In this

context successful multiculturalism usually refers to the success of good integration and assimilation policies rather than a theoretical idea from which to construct ethical policy. This is echoed by Winter, who reviews the success of Canada's famous multiculturalism immigration policy and integration of policies around the province of Quebec. Evidence of multiculturalism is used as proof that the policies on immigration and integration, both external and internal, succeeded.^v

The field of identity politics is slowly gaining popularity in political science and IR with an increasing influence on the shaping the 21st political discourse. Two examples of how multiculturalism fits into this context are given in the articles "The rise and fall of multiculturalism? New debates on inclusion and accommodation in diverse societies" By Will Kymlicka^{vi} and "Pluralism, multiculturalism and the nation-state: rethinking the connections" By William E. Connolly^{vii}. Both articles dive into the field of identity politics explain the political world in terms of how multiculturalism affects identity and how identity affects people's political actions. For example, Kymlicka goes into depth about how identity politics influences people's participation in political actions. This plays out within different nation states that wish to either champion minorities' rights or limit immigration policy.^{viii} Kymlicka discusses the complexities and shifts that we have seen from the early 90s until 2010 and how these have shaped the ideas of identity policies and how they applied to political science research. Connolly raises a different debate about policy. He argues that multiculturalism may become a good alternative system to the current pluralistic one embodied by Christian America.^{ix} He brings up the debate around how multiculturalism is a better way to analyse political events than the

currently used pluralism as multiculturalism has a wider scope to add various political actors needed in understanding identity politics of the 21st century.^x

The article “What went wrong with liberal multiculturalism?” By Rainer Bauböck^{xi} and “Can there be a ‘critical’ multiculturalism?” By Gregor McLennan^{xii} are critics on Kymlicka’s theory of neo liberal multiculturalism. Bauböck’s main line of argumentation is that neo-liberal multiculturalism is not compatible with the needed practicality found in international law of arbitration.^{xiii} While giving merit to the concept of a multicultural society Bauböck is not arguing against the idea in itself but rather that it is a bad theory because Kymlicka’s ideas go against the current Westphalian system and thus, if practised, would create immediate conflict.^{xiv} Therefore, Bauböck is of the opinion that although multiculturalism is good in theory, in practice one must take care how the theory is formulated into policy.^{xv} McLennan has a similar idea to Bauböck’s and is critical of multicultural theory and believes it is problematic due to its strong culturist nature.^{xvi} He claims that this limits true multiculturalism within society as it often tries to prove labels and in doing so hurts the theory of multiculturalism itself.^{xvii} McLennan concludes that multiculturalism itself needs a new framework that is not so militantly culturist centred and is flexible enough to deal with the broad spectrum needed to deal with studying cultures and societies.^{xviii}

One interesting find is an article in the field of Psychology titled “Why Is Multiculturalism Good?” by Blaine J. Fowers and Frank C. Richardson.^{xix} In this context multiculturalism is a moral movement that is intended to enhance the dignity, rights, and recognized worth of marginalized groups.^{xx} The authors argue that multiculturalism is good for human behaviour and that it should be more widely studied in the field of psychology replacing the Euro-American view and approach within the field.^{xxi} This is an interesting article that shows just how widely the term multiculturalism can

be used and its usefulness in other fields not traditionally related to the term. This is also seen in “Multicultural Experiences: A Systematic Review and New Theoretical Framework” by William W. Maddux, Jackson G. Lu, Salvatore J. Affinito and Adam D. Galinsky.^{xxii}

Their extensive study explores how a multicultural society has affected our cognitive behaviour in society as a result of globalisation, and how this phenomenon is shaping our society more generally. These ideas came from earlier research by the article “Relational-Cultural Theory: A Framework for Bridging Relational, Multicultural, and Social Justice Competencies” By Dana L. Comstock, Tonya R. Hammer, Julie Strentzsch, Kristi Cannon, Jacqueline Parsons, and Gustavo Salazar II.^{xxiii} The authors explain how a lack of multicultural and feminist theory in the field of psychology has led to the misdiagnosis of women, people of colour and marginalized groups. Their main argument is that these groups need to be more included in studies to get a better representation of their backgrounds to help build a wider range of possible behavioural patterns which will decrease current bias found in psychology.

The literature review did not reveal any papers that define or test the concept of historic multiculturalism. An interesting starting point to develop an understanding how multiculturalism could be used as a theoretical framework of analysis is in the PhD thesis by John Lowe “Developing a framework for researching ethnicity and multiculturalism in New Zealand”.^{xxiv} This thesis is a great example of research that uses a framework of analysis to investigate the multicultural society of New Zealand and its issues with racism and integration of immigrants from Asia and the Pacific Islands.^{xxv} Lowe’s work is a good example of how to build a framework in studying racism, integration and assimilation with a 21st century multicultural society. However, Lowe’s work must be tweaked further for it to be applied in the field of history.

One way of doing this would be to use defi-

nitions of multiculturalism from the article, “A review of articles on multiculturalism in 35 years of IJIR” by Lily A. Arasaratnam.^{xxvi} Arasaratnam reviews the literature on how multiculturalism has been studied and puts together a comprehensive overview of how multiculturalism has been used within social sciences. Useful for the building of a framework for historic multiculturalism is how the term multiculturalism has been interpreted mainly in education and social studies around identity.^{xxvii} First Frist presented in 1970, Arasaratnam’s ideas about how to define multiculturalism is a good place to start for anyone wanting to define multiculturalism. Arasaratnam developed ideas from the article Multicultural Education Some Issues,^{xxviii} written by Carl J. Dolce. Dolce’s article explores the issues around respecting other cultures.^{xxix} Dolce claims that one cannot respect a different culture with words alone and therefore must also actively support its existence as well.^{xxx} Arasaratnam takes this debate and crafts a useful definition which says multiculturalism is a

reflection of a value system which emphasizes acceptance of behavioural differences deriving from differing cultural systems and actively supports the right of such differences to exist.^{xxxi}

From these definitions this research can create a good theoretical framework of analysis for testing multiculturalism in a historical context and a method of research, defining multiculturalism as a society that accepts, supports and actively allows other cultures to express themselves in civic or daily life. Thus, a historian can set parameters when testing for evidence of what will be coined historic multiculturalism. This gives the historian the building blocks needed to construct a theoretical framework of analysis from which to analyse a society, city or territory. Therefore, one will be able to claim that evidence of historic multiculturalism exists if there is a presence of two or more cultures in a city or territory that were accepted, supported, and publicly allowed to express themselves.

The Location of Vinnytsia First Castle, Page 305: Uncovering Vinnytsia’s Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Methodology

By defining historic multiculturalism as the existence of two or more cultures that were accepted, supported, and could publicly express themselves in civic or public life, one can set parameters for a historic multiculturalism theoretical framework of analysis. The presence of historic multiculturalism can be justified by the meeting of three criteria:

- 1: The presence of different cultures living within the same city or territory.
- 2: Evidence that the different cultures received state support or support from prominent members from society to meet their needs.
- 3: Cultures must be able to freely express themselves in public life without hindrance.

One way to test for historic multiculturalism would be to look at city demographics during a time period. This would be an excellent way for providing evidence that supports the first criterion. However, the demographic data alone does not offer insight into the second and third criteria. Accurate demographic data can be difficult to find in historical sources and in order to make testing for the presence of historic multiculturalism more accurate and easier to verify this research will investigate a city's architectural heritage in key historical eras of that city or territory. By analysing the types of architecture during each era one can test if the three criteria are met. Architecture provides hard evidence found in a city long after that historical era has ended and its remains can easily be verified through established methods in both history and archaeology. In this research architectural evidence is used instead of demographic data to show whether multiple cultures were able to build

and express their cultural identity through unique architectural styles in order to test the conditions of our analytical framework.

The Ukrainian city of Vinnytsia located in central Ukraine makes a good pilot case to test the above framework of analysis because of the city's unique and changing architectural landscape. Modern day Vinnytsia has architectural heritage from four eras: the Polish-Lithuania Commonwealth, Russian Empire, Soviet Union and post-modern eras. Therefore, the research can look how the architectural landscape changed over time and how much influences minority communities had on this landscape. The reason for choosing Vinnytsia is its long historic footprint with the city being established due to favourable agricultural conditions and its strategic location along the Boh River which gave the city a natural defence against invaders. The city established itself as a trading hub first with the river and, with construction of a railway line in 19th century, led to many different cultures to immigrate into the city. With this history there is a high chance the city could be classified as a multicultural one.

To meet the criteria set out by historic multiculturalism theoretical framework of analysis this research will set the changing of the era and governing authorities related to that era as the independent variables. The dependent variable will be the changes in the number of different buildings belonging to different cultures and corresponding architectural styles found in these buildings. To test conditions of historic multiculturalism, as set by the three criteria, the hypothesis statement is: historical multiculturalism is present in Vinnytsia if, first, our research finds evidence of different cultures living in Vinnytsia and that this can be shown through different buildings or archi-

tectural styles related to the different cultures. Secondly, there must be evidence that these different cultures received state support or support from prominent members from society. Lastly, these different cultures could express their differences through the building of different architectural styles associated with their cultures without hindrance.

The method of investigation is through conducting primary source interviews accompanied with photographic evidence from both archives and the present day to help visualize our work. The interviews will be conducted from the following people: local tour guides, local university professors in history from both Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University and Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University, the Head archi-

vist of the regional state archive, local historians from Vinnytsia History Centre and local city workers and architects affiliated with the city's department of urban development. This will be backed up with the limited English secondary sources that exist. Hence, the reliance on a wide range of so many interviews used as the main research material during this investigation.

One main limitation with the multiculturalism theoretical framework of analysis is that it is not able to take into account income inequality or the rigid class system seen in the city of Vinnytsia's history. Though the base conclusions of our findings will not change, one major factor for buildings development during each era was wealth and this can be strongly reflected in architecture. The wealthy were able

Jewish Prayer Tower Used to Celebrate Sukkot, Page 296: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

to pay for buildings and more often than not determined the trendiest architectural styles whereas the poor built buildings from what materials they could find or afford. During the later Russian Empire Vinnytsia experienced a middleclass boom and this explains why the city has a lot of its architectural heritage from this era. Nevertheless, though wealth plays a major fact in the developing of the city's architecture as it is a primary factor for development. It is however, difficulty to shape it into a controllable variable useful tool of analysis in the investigation due to high levels of income inequity. Though one could also argue that seeing the distribution of wealth among different cultures may help strengthen any arguments of multiculturalism in at least the top echelons of citizens as they are paying for the majority of the buildings in the city.

Another limitation of this investigation is the number of sources; there is not a large amount of published literature about the city of Vinnytsia's architectural history. This becomes even smaller when one looks for English or international literature. Thus, most of our information will come from conducting interviewing experts about the city's history. Due

to time and translation resources limitations the quantity of information uncovered may be limited.

To summarise, this research investigates whether the presence of historic multiculturalism can be found in Vinnytsia as classified by the three criteria. We look for evidence of the existence of different cultures in different eras as demonstrated by different buildings and different cultural/architectural styles within these buildings. Furthermore, we test that these cultures received state support or support from prominent members of society and that they these cultures could openly express themselves during the Polish-Lithuania Commonwealth Era, Russian Empire Era, Soviet Union Era, and in the current urban projects of the city. This sets the changing of time periods and governing authorities as the independent variables and the changes in the number of different buildings belonging to different cultures and corresponding architectural styles found on these buildings as the dependent variable. If the conditions of the historic multiculturalism theoretical framework of analysis are met, Vinnytsia can claim to have evidence of historic multiculturalism.

Remains of The Old City Wall (Mury) Built By Kalinowski, Page 308: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Vinnytsia Early History

The chronological of Vinnytsia begins in the 14th century when earliest records of the city's existence are first found.^{xxxvii} Vinnytsia was under the control of the Duchy of Lithuania and was a frontier outpost for defence against the Polish and the Tatars.^{xxxviii} Therefore, the earliest architectural structures found in Vinnytsia are defensive. A castle is found on castle mount and is one of the oldest structures in the city.^{xxxix} The castle was first built as a motte-and-bailey castle, that is to say a wooden keep was surrounded by a stockade with earth ramparts surrounding the structure.^{xl} Unfortunately this defensive structure was not able to deter attacks and the city was continuously raided by Tatars. These raids are one of the significant reasons why in 1569, Vinnytsia was given to the Polish under the terms of the Union of the Lublin treaty. Polish Nobleman would take control of the territory, and in return they agreed to fortify the city and strengthen its defences.^{xli} During the 16th and 17th century the Polish rebuilt the castle in stone and expanded the city limits to include territory on the left bank of the river building with a city wall and two new castles.^{xlii} One of these castles is on the island of Kempa and the second is between the Island Kempa and the main castle on castle mount.^{xliiii} Up until the 18th century Vinnytsia played a crucial role in defending the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth from Tatar raids.^{xliiii}

The expansion over the river was done during the leadership of Walenty Aleksander Kalinowski, originally a Ukrainian/Ruthenia headman (lord) and later became Polish.^{xliiii} Kalinowski expanded the city limits over the Southern Bog and commissioned the above castles and a Jesuit monastery complex which was finished around 1624.^{xliiii} The complex was surrounded by a thick brick wall called Mury

which was built to protect the priests and inhabitants inside.^{xliiii} During the time of his reign, 1604 to 1613, Kalinowski ruled over an economically flourishing city that attracted many merchants, scientists, artists, artisans and the like. The strong defences were also needed to protect Vinnytsia's rich agricultural lands and its profits due to its connection with the medieval salt trade.^{xliiii} The area suffered from constant Tatars raids and was not spared from the political instability within the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth caused by Bohdan Khmelnytsky's Cossack uprising.^{xliiii}

The main architectural style during this 17th and then 18th century was baroque which came from Europe through the influence of the catholic church, the dominant religion at the time.^{xliiii} It's estimated that 90 percent of the buildings in Vinnytsia's early history were built from wood^{xliiii} as wood was much easier to find and process than granite stone which was much more difficult to use.^{xliiii} Only defensive structures like castles or city walls and some religious buildings were built in stone and thus, are still seen in Vinnytsia today. Many churches in Vinnytsia were first built with wood in baroque style^{xliiii} and later in the 18th century rebuilt in stone. During the 18th century the city centre began to form around the Dominican monastery and Jesuit monastery.^{xliiii} The centre was built under European medieval town planning with a central market square surrounded by a town hall, a court and religious buildings.^l In the case of Vinnytsia there were a Jesuit monastery, a Dominican monastery and an Orthodox monastery of the Ascension.^{li} There was also a synagogue built to accommodate the growing Jewish community that were arriving during this era.^{lii} Defence was the main factor in design for the new centre for it was built on a peninsula and thus was

protected by the river on three sides.^{liii} This led to all the above communities, Polish, Ukrainian, Jews and other minorities like Russian or German, to feel protected.^{liv} This arrangement of the city's defences is one of the strongest pieces of evidence found in Vinnytsia's early history that can justify the existence of historical multiculturalism.

With further exploration of 18th century Vinnytsia with the historical multiculturalism framework of analysis the clearest evidence of the Vinnytsia's multiculturalism lies in the fact that the main religious buildings were built next to each other with the city's defences, showing unity and solidarity among Catholic, Orthodox and Jewish communities. This meets the first criterion set out by the historical multiculturalism framework of analysis. One can see that the placing of these religious buildings within the city's defence network meant that the governing authorities believed it worth protecting them all. Stronger evidence of unity between these communities is that some sections of the walls or defences were maintained and defended by the different communities.^{lv} Within modern IR theory this could be seen as early evidence of a society structured around collective defence theory.^{lvi}

Given their religious nature its quite clear that the religious buildings have different Architectural styles. This can be seen by the two remaining buildings present today, the Dominican and Jesuit cathedrals. Style was the main source to differentiate religions at the time. The Catholic church used architectural styles as a way of showing the people in Vinnytsia the beauty of European or western Catholicism and to assert their religious hegemony in the city.^{lvii} The same would be true for the Ascension Monastery of the orthodox faith, which was the heart for the Ukrainians of that time, and the choral synagogue for the Jewish community. Though these faiths were not trying to assert religious hegemony, they still would have used style to differentiate themselves from the Catholics.

When looking for evidence of the second criterion, state support or support from prominent members of society during the 18th century, it is very hard to find support for each individual community as there is little documentary evidence. Though there is evidence of some legal disputes over land and fragments of some architectural design, most of the documents date back to the earlier 19th century.^{lviii} There is little in terms of hard documentary evidence that would show whether or not there was state support for the building of different types of religious buildings. The only account of state support that can be found is Kalinowski commissioning the building of the Jesuit complex and the city wall to protect it when Vinnytsia was expanding to the left side of the river.^{lix} This may look like the state was funding one religion over the others; however, this is hard to say as the building of the wall and subsequent defences around the city would have created the environment in which other religious buildings were able to exist. Thus, the building of the city wall could be seen as an indirect form of state support for each community. Therefore, given the complexity and lack of hard documentary evidence it is hard to conclude in how far state support went in supporting the different religious and ethnic communities during 18th century Vinnytsia.

When looking for evidence for the third criterion, whether the different cultures could express themselves openly through the building of different architectural styles associated with their cultures without hinderance, it is clearly met through the discussion above concerning the different religious buildings built in the 18th century Vinnytsia city centre. While the Catholic community may have had religious hegemony in expressing their culture it did not hinder the other main cultural groups, Ukrainians under Orthodoxies and the Jewish community, from being able to express their cultures by the building of their religious building within the city limits. There is also a second example which helps to strengthen the evidence for the third criterion. The Jewish community built houses with verandas during the

18th century^{lx} with the purpose of celebrating Sukkot, a religious holiday where the household must have a shelter with a hole in the roof in order to see the night sky while they pray.^{lxi} Evidence of these verandas can still be found in Vinnytsia's neighbourhoods of Yerusalimka and new Yerusalimka^{lxii}. The existence of these verandas is clear evidence that the Jewish community felt safe to express their culture through the building of these verandas.

In summary, Vinnytsia's early history has quite clear evidence of historical multiculturalism as defined in the historic multiculturalism framework of analysis. This is in large part because Vinnytsia was built primarily for defence as seen by its earlier architecture consisting mainly of castles and fortifications. Later in the 18th century this played a crucial role in the design of the city which led to the city cen-

tre having three religious buildings from three distinct cultures developing in close proximity to each other. These buildings were also intertwined into the city's defence network showing the value the communities placed on these buildings. The discovery of Jewish verandas used to celebrate Sukkot only points to more evidence that historical multiculturalism can indeed be found in 18th century Vinnytsia. Due to a lack of hard documentation evidence the second criterion regarding state support given to different communities becomes hard to prove with the historical evidence and narrative that we have. Nevertheless, it is quite clear that during the 18th century one can find clear evidence of historical multiculturalism in Vinnytsia.

Old Jesuit Cathedral and Modern Day State Archives, Page 307: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Vinnytsia Golden Age

The late 19th and early 20th century saw a golden age in Vinnytsia's architectural heritage. Evidence can be found by walking around the city as many of today's famous landmarks, such as the water tower (1912) and the Savoy Hotel (1913), were built during this time under mayor Ovodov and head architect Artynov.^{lxxiii} There is also a large collection of archival material of drawings, plans, external drawings of buildings.^{lxxiv} The primary place of where these documents are kept is the City Council archival collection of Vinnytsia's residents' applications for permits for construction, reconstruction, and repairs to their houses. This collection also has hosts many of Artynov's works which shows different drawings and pictures of architecture buildings created at that time.^{lxxv} The reason for this explosion in building can be linked to four main influential factors. The first was the organising of the city through an official city plan. This is first seen in 1790 with the creation of the "Ordinance of Vinnytsia"^{lxxvi} which contains topics related to; how to build on the city's territory, how to ensure fire safety in the city and how to build buildings according to certain canons.^{lxxvii} In 1830, Tsar Nicholas I issued a building charter which established rules for construction of cities within his empire leading to administrative standards in many cities.^{lxxviii}

The second and most influential factor was the building of the railway line between Kyiv and Obessa in 1871 which also included Vinnytsia.^{lxxix} The economic boom seen after the building of the station helped grow Vinnystia to become an important city in the region but also led to a cultural and educational one as well.^{lxxx} The trickle-down effects from the economic boom led to our third influential factor, education and a rise of enlightenment thinking. In 1889, Vinnytsia built the first boys college followed by a female gymnasium which was

built for the rising middle class looking for upward mobility through education.^{lxxxi} This saw the rise in the number of well-educated people in the city and as a consequence the desire to spend their money on building projects that emphasized status. Hence, many public works had aesthetics in mind to show the wealth of the middle class especially the successful merchants.^{lxxxii} This rise in education also saw a rise in enlightened thinking. Evidence to support this claim can be seen by the construction of public libraries in 1903.^{lxxxiii} Following this was the construction of the city theatre in 1910 and the Savoy Hotel in 1913^{lxxxiv} which further enriched the city's cultural life.

This era also saw the building of public works like the city's water tower which improved the water quality and sanitation of the city.^{lxxxv} There was also a powerplant built which brought electricity to the city and powered the Savoy Hotel's elevator which made Vinnytsia very famous at the time.^{lxxxvi} The final piece of evidence that shows evidence of enlightened thinking was that Artinov, and many fellow architects or civil engineers as they were then called, graduated from St. Petersburg institutions. St Petersburg was seen at the time as the cultural heart of the Russian imperial era and all the latest ideas would have been discussed there.^{lxxxvii} This is also why many of the buildings in Vinnytsia built during the early 20th century reflect designs also seen in St Petersburg and points to evidence of European enlightened thinking.

The fourth influential factor that created Vinnytsia's architectural golden age was the excellent management skills of Artinov and his counterpart Ovodov. In the mythology of the city the two are seen as an exceptional duo; however, it is clear that Artinov was the main character who led the successful building of

many of the city's buildings during this time^{lxxxviii}. It is better to analyse Artinov as a cross between an urbanist and architect for he did more than just design buildings and was heavily involved in city planning.^{lxxxix} Artinov understood that a successful city needed to take into account the needs of different communities living within the city. An example of this is the building of a synagogue for Ashkenazi Jews in 1903 which he designed by taking ideas from their culture.^{lxxx} A second example is the city council building on Soborna street^{lxxxi} which Artinov designed in 1911 with the goal of demonstrating the splendour and success of the city authorities at the time.^{lxxxii} The public works, a water management systems, production of electricity and public libraries were all built under Artinov. When one looks at archival records left by Artinov. They show many beautiful aesthetically pleasant documents there to look at and read: "Architect G.G. Artinov approved".^{lxxxiii} These documents, drawn up on blue paper, are a composite image and can unfold into several sheets showing the amount of time, skill and professionalism Artinov placed into his work.^{lxxxiv} This provides more evidences of just how successful Artinov was at managing the city's urban development and the impact he had during Vinnytsia's architectural Golden age in the 19th and 20th century.^{lxxxv}

When one further examines the different architectural styles in Vinnytsia during the 19th and 20th century one finds a shift from Baroque, which was the dominant style commonly found in the 18th century, to more neoclassical design styles^{lxxxvi} found predominantly on country estates and rich inner city houses.^{lxxxvii} The houses first built during the late 19th century were one to two story buildings with a decorative arch on top which would be used to cover the mezzanine floor or attic.^{lxxxviii} The cause of this shift is simple, in 1792 the second partition of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth ended a war between the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth and the Russian Empire.^{lxxxix} Under the treaty Vinnytsia

came under Russian Imperial control which in turn started to shape the region according to its norms^{xc} and thus, the neoclassical style of architecture started to become more common.

In the early 20th century the neoclassical architecture in Vinnytsia was slowly replaced by the Art Nouveau style which was originally an ornamental style of art which flourished between 1890 and 1910.^{xc} Art Nouveau is characterized by its use of a long, sinuous, organic line and employed in many different artistic professions including architecture.^{xcii} One good example of the Art Nouveau style in Vinnytsia is the old boys college, built in 1889, which today is the Vinnytsia University of Economics and Trade.^{xciii} One unique local feature in Vinnytsia's architecture or building materials during the 19th and 20th century was the use of locally mined silicate bricks as decoration. They were usually either white, red and green and used to indicate wealth of the individual who owned the building.^{xciv}

The Jewish verandas used to celebrate Sukkot are still present in the 20th century but are transformed by the rise of the wealthy Jewish middleclass, such as businessmen like Baruch Moisevich Lvovich, saw the construction of prayer towers with an open roof to celebrate Sukkot. However, many of these Jewish buildings were decorated with styles of the time eg, neoclassical or Art Nouveau style.^{xcv} This fact limits this research as discussed during the methodology section for many wealthy people wanted to show wealth rather than their own culture. For in the 19th and 20th century architecture in Vinnytsia was about social status rather than a cultural identifier as seen in earlier eras. People simply wanted to show many different coloured silicate bricks or having their houses decorated with neoclassical styled architecture and later with Art Nouveau styled architecture. When one looks at the middle class in Vinnytsia, they too used architecture to show at least parts of the latest architectural style showing that the owner of the building had some wealth. Therefore,

because of this environment it's hard to argue to what extent the first criterion is met. For if one looks at who was building rather than the styles then one finds evidence of wealthy Jewish families decorating their houses with neoclassical styled architecture and later with Art Nouveau styled architecture as an open expression of their wealth rather than cultural styles. Therefore, one must conclude that there were few different cultural styles represented through architecture during the 19th and 20th century in contrast to 18th century Vinnytsia and thus there is less evidence to meet the first criterion.

The work of Artinov in successfully building the city to meet the needs of different cultural groups is good evidence of the second criterion. However, this must be weighed against the anti-Semitic laws passed during the reign of Catherine II in 1762 – 1796 which divided the Russian empire into zones for the resettlement of Jewish people.^{xcvi} These laws saw the right bank of Vinnytsia become the home for many poor Jews who built the Yerusalimka district in Vinnytsia.^{xcvii} In the early 20th century this

anti-Semitism began to recede with the rise of enlightenment ideas under which Ukrainians wished for more self-governance.^{xcviii} This period saw the Jewish community begin to prosper as seen by the rise of Jewish businessmen Baruch Moisevich Lvovich.^{xcix} This reduction of anti-Semitism also coincides with Artinov's two clearest examples of state support. The design and building of the synagogue for Ashkenazi Jews in 1903 and the construction of the city's water tower to improve water management and sanitation for the city's poor who were mostly Jewish. If one examines the scope of prominent members from society during the 19th and 20th century. The Jewish businessmen Baruch Moisevich Lvovich did finance the construction of a few buildings connected to his business but there is no clear link that they were built for the benefit for a single culture or just the city in general. Therefore, with Vinnytsia's rise in enlightenment ideas and Artinov successful public works and urban planning of Vinnytsia. Even with the earlier legacy of anti-Semitic laws passed by Catherine II during her region. One can still find sufficient evidence during the earlier 20th

Remains Of A Jewish Veranda Used to Celebrate Sukkot, Page 320: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

century that meets the second criteria set out by our framework.

Even with the passing of Catherine's II anti-Semitic laws construction of religious symbols and buildings were not hindered so long as they were in the correct area. Therefore, districts like Yerusolimka saw the building of synagogues like the one for the Ashkenazi Jews in 1903. The district also saw the widespread placement of religious symbols on private homes.⁶ This would imply that open expression of cultural differences for Jewish people was possible to some extent providing evidence that the third criterion is met.

In summary, the late 19th and earlier 20th century history has made a large contribution to Vinnytsia's rich architectural heritage. The building of the railway station supported the late 19th century economic boom and the subsequent rise in education led to the perfect environment for a man like Artinov

to carry out his work. The strongest evidence of historic multiculturalism during this era is the rise of prominent Jewish businessmen like Baruch Moisevich Lvovich rising in status and influence parallel to the work carried out by Artinov. This resulted in the building of the synagogue for Ashkenazi Jews in 1903 and the construction of the city's water tower and shows that during the early 20th century minority cultures could openly express their wealth through the popular styles of architectures. There was also attention given to what would benefit the city's residents, including minority communities, through the building of public works. The building of public works to improve citizens health and standard of living can be compared to the 18th century Vinnytsia which saw different communities engaging in collective defence, also providing evidence of a multicultural society. Therefore, despite the wealth limitation one can argue that the late 19th and earlier 20th century has enough evidence to argue the fulfilling of all three criteria.

Old Boys College and Now Vinnytsia University of Economics and Trade, Page 317:
Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Soviet Legacy and Post-modern Vinnytsia

In 1917, with the collapse of the Russian Empire and the start of the Bolshevik Revolution, Vinnytsia became the temporary capital of the Independent Ukrainian Republic as Ukraine fought for its independence until 1921.^{ci} With the victory of the Bolshevik army, Vinnytsia's architectural landscape began to change as the Bolshevik began systematically destroying churches and renovating buildings they deemed too bourgeois.^{cii} The Soviet era can be divided into many different sub eras depending on the type of soviet architecture present. The first type can be labelled as the Stalin period which saw various administrative buildings being built.^{ciii} The buildings were used to show the distinct Stalinist character which can be called totalitarian architecture, Stalin's Baroque or Stalin's Empire.^{civ} These styles were used to show power and strength while also being a dominating feature on the landscape to give a feeling of awe and fear to those who saw the buildings.^{cv} In 1934, A.D. Gurovich and his team began renovating the city of Vinnytsia by widening and cobbling the main roads of Lenin Street, now Soborna St and Dzerzhinsky Street, now Teatralna St.^c
^{vi} In addition, they also started building many parks and squares and in 1936 Gurovich's team designed the Gorky Central park of culture.^{cvi}

The second style to follow the Stalin period can be labelled as the Khrushchev period.^{cviii} During this period the Vyshenka neighborhood was constructed with the famous soviet five-story buildings.^{cix} These apartment blocks were designed to provide accommodation for people who were resettled in the city.^{cx} These new apartments had a room of 30-43 square meters because the task of a good Soviet man was to wake up in the morning, wash, eat and go to the factory, build communism and not ask any questions.^{cx} Following this Khrushchev period are three new stages, which have

be described and theorized by the architect Eugene Savinsky. Each of the stages had its own characteristics and their precise divisions are still widely discussed.^{cxii}

Some of Vinnytsia most iconic buildings built during the later Soviet era is the white arch at the main entrance of Gorky Central park of culture designed by architect Roman Markhel and finished in 1961.^{cxiii} The old Ministry of Agriculture of the USSR and the current city council building were designed by Petro Antonik.^{cxiv} The Knyzhka ("book" because of its architecture design looking like a book)^{cxv} was designed by architect Vladyslav Horbatyi. Construction of the Knyzhka is thought to have been started 1979 and finished in 1986.^{cxvi} And, lastly, the cinema "Russia".^{cxvii} What is unique about cinema Russia is that it has a built-in panoramic view of the surrounding nature and many design styles would be difficult to replicate today.^{cxviii}

When one looks for evidence of the three criteria within the Soviet architectural era it becomes clear that the Soviets were not in favour of allowing individual expression.^{cxix} As stated above the purpose of the architecture was to show power and authority. The Soviets were also in favour of making everything as standardised and as efficient as possible through their construction design. Later their buildings incorporated the ability to hold social functions and promote equity among the people.^{cxx} Therefore, when applying the first criterion, it is no surprise that one does not find any different styles due to the aims of Soviet architecture. Soviet architecture did have many different styles depending on the time period so labelling all soviet architecture as one style would be incorrect. This still would fall short as all the stylistic choices still follow the repressive ideology of soviet architecture.

When looking for evidence of the second criterion, evidence of state support or support from prominent members of society, the two can be classified as the same in the Soviet era where all prominent members were in the party and thus political figures as well. This era would see the most state support for architecture and public works. Given the nature of Soviet design it's hard to argue that it was done to enhance the welfare of other cultures as they believed in creating equity and uniformity through state sponsored work.

Given the results of the first two criteria the third criterion is likely also not met given the nature of Soviet architecture design and purpose. However, it might be in this criterion that a small amount of light can shine through. One example that provides evidence of the third criterion is the white arch with an arrow at the entrance to the Central Park - a work of genius architect Roman Markhel.^{cxvi} Markhel is discovered to have left behind a number of projects of such a modernist trend.^{cxvii} When historians from Vinnytsia History Centre researched his archive they found that he was illegally familiar with architectural magazines from abroad.^{cxviii} It is believed Markhel drew inspiration from certain projects and try to integrate them into his work thus, endeavouring to go beyond the authoritarian state which tried to control all spheres of society.^{cxix}

A second example that supports the third criterion is the presence of Soviet mosaics that adorn the city buildings.^{cxv} The main buildings on which they are primarily found are educational institutions, factories, places of rest and transportation stops (e.g. bus stops). In the Soviet era, mosaics became an expression of the individuality of the city, both in the monumental and in the artistic sense.^{cxvi} Therefore, one could consider these mosaics as self-expression for artist who may have placed their individuality in the mosaics while also hiding it from the authoritarian state.^{cxvii} While this idea cannot be proven indefinitely in the case of Roman Markhel some evidence to support

this claim may be found. Though subsequent historical investigations will need to be carried out to verify this hypotheses. In light of these two examples one can see that even under the Soviet era Vinnytsia still had a slight presence of multiculturalism, but not enough to justify the existence of historic multiculturalism as set out by the framework used.

Given the history of the Soviet era the number of citizens in Vinnytsia who perceive the Soviet legacy as very negative.^{cxviii} Despite the negative sentiment, the city of Vinnytsia does benefit from what the Soviets left behind, such as many of the city's large spaces, wide roads, good sewers, and many buildings with large public space surrounding them^{cxix} which makes redesign for modern day Vinnytsia much easier than in some old medieval European cities.^{cx} This legacy from the Soviets can be considered a primary factor in reviving Vinnytsia's historic multiculturalism because of its role in now two major renovation and redesign projects carried out by local government today. The first project is the repurposing of the old CRYSTAL factory, originally the old jewellery factory of the city, into the CRYSTAL Innovation and Technology park.^{cxxi} The prime goal of this project is to stimulate the growing ICT sector in Vinnytsia which is currently ranked in the top six ICT cities in Ukraine and hopes to be in the top three in the coming years.^{cxvii}

The goal of the CRYSTAL Tech park is to build a modern, functional, and inclusive space for all Vinnytsia citizens while at the same time grow the city's ICT ecosystem.^{cxviii} The Tech park has over 8500 m² of space and will include: Fab Lab and laboratories, Business Development Centre, IT-School, offices, a conference hall, coworking, public spaces, and a Children's Technology Centre.^{cxix} There will also be 1000+ m² left for event space which the city needs to hold larger events.^{cx} This shows just how useful all that public space left by the Soviets can be for turning it into something positive for a post-Soviet city. The CRYSTAL

project also plans to restore the factory's old mosaic because good or bad Soviet history is still a part of the city's history and thus needs to be preserved.^{cxxxvi}

The second project that is being planned by various entities of Vinnytsia's local government is the establishment of an Intercultural House of Europe.^{cxxxvii} The idea was first conceived by Oleksandr Korotkikh, previously head architect of Vinnytsia. He suggested to refurbish the old Soviet cinema Russia and transform it into the Intercultural House of Europe.^{cxxxviii} This idea was added to Vinnytsia's Intercultural Strategy which is a collection of projects that enable Vinnytsia to be one of the six intercultural cities in Ukraine.^{cxxxix} The goal of the Intercultural House of Europe will be to create a hub of intercultural activity by providing event space for conferences, coworking spaces and spaces for education or workshops.^{cxl} The plan is to host the Polish consulate offices inside the Intercultural House of Europe in the hope that it will lead to other minority groups using the space as well.^{cxli} The architectural design would of course reflect a modern design and focus on functionality rather than any specific architectural design.^{cxlii} If this project is to go ahead it would become evidence of not only a positive legacy left behind by the

Soviet, but also evidence of historic multiculturalism as defined by our framework of analysis.

Thus, when one looks at modern day Vinnytsia, the city has a diverse architectural history of buildings dating back from the 18th century, 19th and earlier 20th century Soviet buildings. The city is also constructing new postmodern high-rises and shopping malls that are now decorating the city's skyline. The Jewish committee, though small, is still alive in Vinnytsia along with other minority communities like Polish, Russian, Georgian and other international communities. Evidence of their presence can be easily seen by the number of different ethnic restaurants found throughout the city.^{cxliii} Thus, if one applies modern day Vinnytsia to our three criteria of historic multiculturalism one will find the city has three distinct religious communities architectural styles as well as defensive structures from the 18th century, neoclassical and Art Nouveau architecture from the 19th and earlier 20th century alongside a few remains of Jewish architecture. There are many different styles of Soviet architecture from the Stalin, Khrushchev and the following periods all with their unique ideas around what Soviet architecture should be, and, lastly, one will find the mod-

White Arch, Gorky Central Park, Page 325: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

ern shopping malls, high-rises and redesigned buildings of the soviet era like the CRYSTAL Park.

When looking for evidence of the second criteria; projects like the CRYSTAL Park and the Intercultural House of Europe make perfect examples of evidence to support the presence of historic multiculturalism, although one could argue that the Intercultural House of Europe is western focused. However, one could also link the project to the fact that the city wishes to achieve the same objectives as what Artinov wanted to provide for the different culture groups in the city. If the Intercultural House of Europe achieves its aim of being a space for the city's minorities it would undoubtedly become the city's largest piece of evidence of historic and probably present-day multiculturalism. When looking for evidence of the third criteria we observe that the aims of the Intercultural House of Europe wanting minority groups to express themselves through its faculties and the large number of ethnic

restaurants scattered through Vinnytsia provide evidence that culture groups can and are encouraged to freely express themselves and thus, meet the conditions of the third criteria.

To summarise, although the Soviet era left a negative impact during their region in Vinnytsia, especially during the Stalin period. The later periods of Soviet architectural history through creation of mosaic and the building designs of Roman Markhel provide a small amount of evidence in this time period to support the claim of the present of historic multiculturalism. However, the bigger discovery is that the legacy of the Soviet architecture left behind has had a positive impact on modern Vinnytsia which is able to transform these old Soviet spaces into positive places for Vinnytsia citizens and its different minority committees and cultural groups that reside in the city. This is by far the most positive aspect of Soviet architecture that directly shapes modern Vinnytsia's present and subsequent claims of historic multiculturalism.

Soviet Building Knyzhka (Book). Page 326: Uncovering Vinnytsia's Architectural Heritage Sourcebook

Conclusions

This research shows how the newly constructed historic multiculturalism framework can be used to analyse historic case studies and validate whether cities or territories had historic multiculturalism present during their history. By investigating our case study of the city of Vinnytsia one finds that there is indeed historic multiculturalism present throughout Vinnytsia's history. One also finds that during Vinnytsia's early history there is a lot of clear evidence of historical multiculturalism that meets the three criteria set out by the framework used to define historical multiculturalism. Vinnytsia's defensive network, consisting mainly of castles and fortifications, played a crucial role in the design of the city which led to the city centre having three religious buildings from which three distinct cultures lived in harmony. The discovery of Jewish verandas used to celebrate Sukkot makes the 18th century Vinnytsia, when analysed by our framework, as the strongest era to have historic multiculturalism.

Vinnytsia late 19th and earlier 20th century have made the largest contribution to the city's rich architectural heritage. The new railway line created an economic boom which led to the rise in education and created the perfect environment for an architect like Artinov. Evidence for historic multiculturalism during the earlier 20th century can be provided by the rise of prominent Jewish businessmen, such as Baruch Moisevich Lvovich, the building of the synagogue for Ashkenazi Jews in 1903 and the construction of the city's water tower by Artinov. Though this era does not have as strong a case as the 18th century era, it does still show enough evidence to justify the presence of historic multiculturalism when analysed by the framework of analysis.

When the Soviet era is analysed by the historic multiculturalism framework it simply doesn't have enough evidence to be considered an era of having historic multiculturalism, due to ideologies behind the construction of Soviet buildings. Only the creation of mosaics and buildings designed by Roman Markhel provide trace amounts of evidence to support the claim of historic multiculturalism. However, the legacy of the Soviet architecture that was left behind in Vinnytsia has undoubtedly directly shaped modern Vinnytsia's claim to the existence of historic multiculturalism.

This makes modern Vinnytsia the most blessed era for having such a rich architectural heritage that points to the existence of historic multiculturalism spanning back to its early history. These findings show that the historic multiculturalism framework of analysis is useful as an analytical tool for researching multiculturalism throughout history and is also well suited in working in historic eras which have limited or incomplete source material. This research hopes to have provided a foundation for further studies interested in looking at the role multiculturalism plays in shaping societies or cities providing opportunity for further study to investigate multiculturalism as a factor that leads cities or societies to flourish and so bring a fresh perspective on understanding the formation of societies.

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